

Fig. 1.1

3D model of Cova Foradada volume. Top (a), frontal (b) and back (c) views view with relative height colour scale, ranging from red (highest) to blue (lowest)

Fig. 2

View of Cova Foradada's the first day of the rescue excavation in 1997

Photo 1997

Fig. 3

View of Cova Foradada's lower entrance leading to the excavation hall.

The image shows the original shape of the external terrace before its excavation in 2014.

The sediment height at the entrance coincides with original level when the excavation started in 1997.

Photo 2006

Fig. 4

Layer I under excavation. The top of the sedimentation reaches the travertine slope at the right of the photo. At the left, the SW Gallery is completely full filled by archaeological sediments.

Photo 2006

Supporting Information 1 – Excavation of the Holocene Layers

Fig. 5

Excavation of Level I (Holocene layers). Opposite view of the Fig. 1.4

Photo 2006

Fig. 6

Progress of the excavation of the Holocene layers. The Travertine Platform 2 starts to appear mainly at squares D6 – D7

The contact between Layer I and Layer II is visible by the sediments colour change on squares E6 – E7. Nevertheless the abundance of burrowing, and probably, the activities related to the Late Neolithic funerary dynamics affected severely the preservation of Layer II.

Photo 2010

Fig. 7

The excavation works of Layer II finished in 2012.

The surface of Travertine Platform 2 expanded, appearing also in squares E6, C 6-7 and B6.

Below the slate board appears the top of the Unit III (squares E9 – D9), posteriorly divided into layers III_n, III_g and III_c.

The effects of the erosive processes affecting the top of Unit III can be seen in squares E7-8 and F8-9, where the yellowish sediment of the Unit III is starting to be uncovered at a much lower depth than in E9 – D9.

Photo 2012

Fig. 8

Following the lateral continuity of the Unit III top lead to the identification of Layer III_n at the NE area of the excavation hall.

Layer III_n was preserved exclusively in squares B6-7 and C6-7. In the rest of excavation surface its identification was impossible, due to erosive dynamics and the sediments mixing during the Holocene occupations later deposited.

Photo 2012

Fig. 9

Layer III n almost excavated. The slope of the calcarenite slab-like fragments indicates a marked dipping to the East.

At the left of the image, extreme of the horizontal rod stick, the top of Layer IIIc is already visible. The hammer and chisels stands on the Travertine Platform 2.

Photo 2012

a)

b)

Fig. 10

Some of the marine pierced seashells recovered from Layer IIIIn. Fig. 10a shows a complete and a fragmented specimen of *Turritella comunis* and a small specimen of *Tritia neritea*. In Fig. 10b one specimen of *Homalopoma sanguineum* with the perforation faced forward.

Photo 2013

Fig. 11

Layer II excavation progresses allowed to document the baseline of the erosive process.

Unit IIIc was preserved in all the excavation hall.

At the image Layer IIIc is already uncovered in squares E–F6-7. Note the progressive enlargement of the SW Gallery. An accumulation of modern depositions was discovered at the end of the gallery.

Photo 2013

Fig. 12

Same surface of Fig. 11 viewed from the lower entrance of the cave. Note the lateral contact between the Travertine Platform 2 and the top of Unit IIIc at the squares E6-7.

In square D7 a large calcarenite boulder appears embedded in the Travertine Platform 2.

Photo 2013

Fig. 13

The top of Layer IIIc appeared still affected by some burrows coming from the upper layers (E7). The identification and isolation was easy due to the clear colour and textural differences between the burrow-filling sediment and the *in situ* Layer IIIc.

Note the abundance of charcoals, some of them larger than 2cm, characteristic at Layer IIIc, and probably derived from the fire features documented at the reference section (E9 – D9).

Photo 2013

Fig. 14

Detail of the previous surface showing a faunal remain and charcoals. This bone was one of the selected for 14C AMS pre-treatment and dating program at MPI-EVA. Unfortunately, no collagen was recovered.

Photo 2013

Jaciment: E13
Data: 21/11/13
Nivell: II Q: E7
Nº

Fig. 15

Fibula of *Panthera pardus* recovered at Layer IIIc, square E8, affected by post-depositional breakage.

Photo 2013

a)

b)

Fig. 16

Layer IIIc surface excavation. 16a, general view of square E7 during the excavation works. Fig. 16b, detail of Dufour bladelet, corresponding with Fig. 13.3 of the manuscript.

Photo 2013

a)

b)

Fig. 17

Fig. 17a, general view of the reference section (E9 – D9) at the end of the excavation of Layer IIIc. Fig. 17b, close view of the interstratification of fire-related (carbonaceous lines and reddened sediment and stones) sediments and unaltered ones.

Fig. 18

General view of the cave, showing the top of Layer IV at the end of 2013 fieldwork season.

Photo 2013

Fig. 19

View of the SW Gallery once all the sediments from the Upper Layers were excavated.

The depth of the surface correlates with the top of Layer IIIc in lines E and F.

Photo 2014

Fig. 20

Detailed view of the large calcareous boulders accumulated in the SW Gallery and the scarcity of sedimentary matrix.

Photo 2014

Fig. 21

Top of the Layer IV exposed at the excavation hall. A complex system of rabbit burrows was documented and emptied before starting with the excavation Layer IV.

Note how the top of Layer IV continues below the Travertine Platform 2.

Photo 2014

Fig. 22

Advancing the excavation of Layer IV. Some of the calcarenite and travertine fragments helping to differentiate Layer IV and sublayer IV1 starts to appear, specially at E7 and D8.

Photo 2014

Fig. 23

First Châtelperronian point uncovered during the excavation of Layer I. Squares E8 – F8 (Fig. 15.1 of the manuscript).

Photo 2014

Fig. 24

Distally fractured Châtelperronian point appeared during the excavation of sublayer IV1 at F8. Fig.15.2 of the manuscript.

Photo 2014

Fig. 25

Faunal remains (*Lynx* cf. *pardinus* radius and rabbit remains) recovered in sublayer IV1 are completely covered by manganese oxide.

Photo 2014

Fig. 26

Accumulation of calcarenite and travertine fragments allowed separating sublayers IV1 and IV2.

Photo 2015

Fig. 27

Top of sublayer IV2 and its relation to the Travertine Platform 2.

Photo 2015

Fig. 28

SW Gallery during the excavation of the Unit IV.

Photo 2015

Fig. 29

Ending the excavation of sublayer IV2. Most of the excavation surface shows the presence of speleothems (E8 – D8) and travertine crusts (E7 – D7).

The sediments from sublayer IV2 percolate between the crevices of the speleothems and travertines.

Photo 2015

Fig. 30

All the excavation surface is at this point occupied by speleothems. The sediment excavated between the crevices and fissures of the speleothem is attributed to Layer V, but it is exclusively paleontological, providing lynx and rabbit remains.

Photo 2015

Fig. 31

General view of the cave after the excavation of the Unit IV at the excavation hall.

At this point, Unit IV is still preserved under the Travertine Platform 2.

Photo 2015

Fig. 32

Reference section at the end of the excavation of the Unit IV at the excavation hall.

Photo 2015

Fig. 33

Section showing the Unit IV preserved and sealed by the Travertine Platform 2.

Photo 2015

Fig. 34

Dismantling the Travertine Platform 2 for the 2017 field season.

Photo 2017

a)

Fig. 35

Section showing the sedimentary sequence preserved below the Travertine Platform 2 after its removal. A thin grey layer of sediments infiltrated through the travertine fissures is deposited at the top of the Unit IV. Fig 35a, frontal view. Fig.35b, top view.

Photo 2017

b)

Fig. 36

Top of the Unit IV preserved under the Travertine Platform 2 after the excavation of the percolated sediments and the emptying of the burrows.

Photo 2017

Fig. 37

Excavation process of the Unit IV preserved under the Travertine Platform 2.

Photo 2017

a)

b)

Fig. 38

Archaeological materials appearing at Unit IV below the Travertine Platform 2. Fig. 38a, Châtelperronian point (Fig. 16.2 of the manuscript). Fig. 38b show a damaged mandible of a neonate *Ursus* sp and other faunal remains.

Photo 2017

Fig. 39

View of the Lower Entrance and the beginning of the terrace's excavation

Photo 2014

Fig. 40

View of the terrace's excavation after the removal of the superficial organic sediments and delimiting the carbonated sedimentary layer.

Photo 2014

Fig. 41

Carbonated sedimentary layer was excavated until the bedrock is reached.

Paleolithic evidences were not documented during the excavation of the external sedimentation.

Photo 2014

Fig. 42

Section of the excavation at the terrace of the Lower Entrance. The stratigraphy is formed by i) superficial sediments, ii) carbonated layer, iii) bedrock.

Photo 2014

a)

Fig. 43

View of the upper test pit on the travertine slope leading to the Upper Entrance, visible in Fig. 43a. Below the travertines the archeo-paleontological unit documented.

Photo 2006

b)

Fig. 44

The excavation of the upper test pit was started over in 2017 together with the exploration of the Upper Entrance.

The 2006 – 2007 excavation of this area reported mainly remains of lynx together with thousands of rabbit and bird remains indicating the use of this space as a lynx den. During the excavation several anthropogenic remains were recovered, including some burned bones and lithic remains.

The chronology of this deposit is still unknown.

Photo 2017

Fig. 45

View of the Upper Entrance of the cave leading to the travertine platform after clearing the vegetation.

Photo 2017

Fig. 46

Large rockfall documented in front of the Upper Entrance presumably related to an ancient collapse of a larger entrance.

Photo 2017

a)

Fig. 47

Expanding the excavation of the Upper Entrance lead to document more large boulders and even documenting the continuity of the inner travertine slope outside the actual cavity.

No fieldwork was done in 2018 to finish the studies of the 2013 – 2017 excavation period. Fieldwork season in 2019 will be focused in this sector of the cave to detect if sealed galleries containing archaeological sequence exist below the travertine formation

Photo 2017

b)

View of the travertine slope from the upper test pit facing outwards. The continuity of the travertines to the exterior of the cave can be seen below the two boulders of the entrance.

Photo 2017

